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Access and Security to Land Through Cooperatives: Insights from Eswatini Women on Drivers, Barriers and Strategies *Cynthia Shabangu*¹; *Prisca Simbanegavi*²; *Koech Cheruiyot*³ and *Partson Paradza*⁴

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Abstract

Eswatini women face considerable barriers in their pursuit of land ownership, which are deeply rooted in a complex interplay of socioeconomic and cultural factors. As such, this paper aims to fill the knowledge gap regarding how cooperatives can act as mechanisms to improve women's access to land. A quantitative methodology was employed, with structured questionnaires distributed to 92 women from seven cooperatives, and the data were analyzed through descriptive statistics and chi-square tests. The paper adopted a quantitative approach and administered questionnaires to women in seven cooperatives. The paper established the critical role that land acquisition plays in enhancing women's economic status, as driven by various factors, such as the need to acquire land to embark on entrepreneurial initiatives that emerged statistically significantly. However, several barriers (statistically significant) hamper the possibility of crowdfunding to enhance women's economic status. The findings reveal that while land ownership is closely associated with economic empowerment, food security, and asset accumulation, women face considerable challenges such as insufficient income, lack of collateral, and restrictive land tenure laws. The study concludes that specific reforms, especially supportive legal frameworks, financial innovations like crowdfunding, and gender-sensitive cooperative models, are essential for promoting women's land rights and empowerment in Eswatini. Financial assistance programs tailored to women's unique needs can also play a crucial role in providing the necessary resources for land acquisition and sustainable development.

Key words: Land Acquisition; Women; Cooperatives; Drivers; Eswatini

Introduction

The rising global demand for commercial and industrial infrastructure has led to significant real estate investment, especially in the residential sector. In rapidly developing economies like China, India, and South Korea, foreign investments have positively impacted market growth (Shahrokhi & Parhizgari, 2020). However, domestic investment remains limited, creating opportunities for women in the sector. The real estate investment landscape includes three dimensions: distribution channels, property types, and investment purposes. Distribution channels consist of public and private investments, similar to trends in Eswatini (Malaga et al. 2018). Property types include commercial, residential, industrial, and land, with commercial investments further divided into retail, office, and recreational spaces (Malaga et al. 2018).

The demand for private capital in real estate is increasing in emerging economies like Eswatini, where urban migration, population growth, and a rising middle class increase the need for urban real estate investments (PWC, 2020; FSRA, 2022). However, high capital requirements pose barriers for many women, particularly those with low incomes (FAO, 2011; World Bank, 2012). Funding sources for real estate investments include traditional bank loans, private lenders, hard money lenders, partnerships, seller financing, and crowdfunding (Shahrokhi &

Parhizgari, 2020; Legenzova & Leckè, 2022). Land-related challenges in Eswatini significantly affect real estate investments, as the King holds all land in trust for the people, and non-residents face land access restrictions (UN Women, 2020). Women can only own land through a child, and most land is classified as Swazi Nation Land (Mutangadura, 2004; Kachika, 2009). To navigate these challenges, women in Eswatini can employ various strategies, such as building networks, fostering collective action, education, and engaging with local and national policymakers (Jacobs, 2004; Rüniger, 2006). Crowdfunding platforms can offer a unique financing option for women in Eswatini, allowing them to access capital for land acquisition and share their stories and projects (Adjakou, 2021; Kunz et al., 2018). The paper focuses on the problem of poor investment in real estate, particularly among women in Eswatini, and the secondary research questions include the drivers of land acquisition for women in stokvels/cooperatives, the barriers faced in acquiring land, and strategies to improve land acquisition efforts. To conceptually frame this study, we utilize Empowerment Theory, specifically Rappaport's (1981) focus on collective action as a strategy for tackling structural inequalities. Empowerment Theory underscores the mechanisms by which marginalized groups obtain resources, enhance their control over decisions that impact their lives, and realize social justice outcomes. In the context of women's cooperatives in Eswatini, this theory serves as a valuable perspective for comprehending how collective agency can confront discriminatory land tenure systems, alleviate financial obstacles, and foster sustainable approaches to land ownership.

Literature Review

Empowering Women Through Land Ownership

Land ownership significantly enhances women's economic empowerment by creating avenues for income generation, asset accumulation, and entrepreneurial ventures. It acts as collateral for obtaining credit and capital, which facilitates the initiation or expansion of businesses. Furthermore, land ownership contributes to food security, as it enables women to participate in agricultural practices to produce food for their families and communities. Additionally, owning land opens opportunities for diversifying income sources through activities such as livestock farming, horticulture, and agro-processing (FAO, 2012). The provision of ownership rights is crucial for the sustainable advancement of agriculture, given that land is a vital resource influencing the economic welfare of peasants (Roy and Tisdell, 2002). Nonetheless, institutional biases persist in numerous developing countries, often privileging men. Land ownership can enhance self-esteem and provide both physical and psychological security, therefore, safeguarding women's land rights may help reduce gender inequalities and diminish women's dependence on men for their livelihoods.

Stability in land tenure is linked to improved food security, particularly for women. Securing and respecting women's land rights can enhance a family's overall access to resources necessary for nutrition and food security, thereby increasing agricultural productivity and promoting shared decision-making within households (Allendorf, 2007). Research indicates that female farmers perform on par with their male counterparts and would achieve similar yields if granted equal access to resources and services. As noted by Agarwal (2007), women's land rights in South Asia empower them to negotiate for less restrictive norms and improved treatment from their spouses.

Barriers to Obtaining Land for Women in Cooperatives

Discriminatory legal frameworks and customary practices often limit women's land ownership and access. Poor enforcement of land laws, along with a lack of financial resources and awareness of funding options like crowdfunding, worsen these challenges (Mubuu, 2013). Sociocultural factors, such as restricted mobility and limited decision-making power, further impede women's ability to secure land. For instance, Saudi Arabia has the lowest female land ownership rate globally, despite women having legal rights under Sharia law (FAO, 2016; Almazi, 2016). Cultural norms favor men in inheritance, and women's educational disadvantages hinder their land acquisition, often leading them to forfeit inheritance to their husbands. In Kenya, cultural resistance to women's land ownership is significant, with 49% of the population opposing it and fewer than 12% believing in women's equal rights to land (Mwagae, 2013). Evidence shows gender disparities in land access, with women less likely to own or manage property or control agricultural resources (FAO, 2011; Deere et al. 2011).

Gender inequality persists in Africa and parts of Asia, with women facing significant barriers to land ownership. In Eswatini, only 20% of landowners are women, a trend worsened by diverse social and economic contexts that restrict women's access to land. Runger (2006) highlights those complex legal systems in Ghana and Kenya disadvantage women in property rights, compounded by lower income and literacy rates. Legal challenges related to marriage and sharecropping further hinder their access. Research indicates that land property rights can empower women and help combat poverty. Mutangadura (2004) identifies the exclusion of women from property ownership as a severe human rights violation, while Kachika (2009) emphasizes the need for women to have full access to land to reduce poverty and meet the Millennium Development Goals.

In Uganda, women are key agricultural producers but face significant challenges in accessing and owning land. Agarwal (2003) notes a "lack of a voiced demand" for independent land rights, with studies focusing more on racial disparities than gender issues. Prevailing gender attitudes affect women's perceptions and use of land, hindering their advancement. This challenge is common in rural areas across Africa, South Asia, Latin America, and the Caribbean. Although customary law in Latin America is less restrictive than in Saudi Arabia, women still face barriers to land ownership due to legal and social frameworks. Historically, while women had land rights, titles were often held by their husbands, and agricultural reforms in the 1970s recognized men as primary producers, reducing women's bargaining power in global markets.

Techniques to Enhance Women's Land Acquisition in Cooperatives

Gender-sensitive land legislation is vital for protecting women's rights and preventing discrimination, requiring transparent title acquisition processes and supportive institutional frameworks (USAID, 2008). Several countries have adopted reforms to strengthen women's land rights: Tanzania guarantees equal succession and marital property rights; Ethiopia includes both spouses on joint land titles; and Guatemala, India, and Mozambique mandate co-registration or recognize women's equal rights to use land. Such measures address poverty, food insecurity, and social inequalities (Stanley et al., 2012). Beyond legal reforms, improving literacy, public awareness, and education empowers women to claim their entitlements. At the same time, crowdfunding has emerged as an innovative strategy to enhance women's land ownership by mobilizing resources and building social networks, though challenges such as high campaign costs remain.

Theoretical Literature Review

The theoretical foundation of this study is anchored in two complementary perspectives, African Feminist Theory and Empowerment Theory.

African Feminist Theory

African Feminist Theory was developed by African women to address their specific socio-cultural challenges and challenge patriarchal systems that perpetuate gender inequality. It emphasizes egalitarian relationships between men and women and aims to dismantle oppressive structures limiting women's access to vital resources like land. This theory highlights that women's marginalization in property ownership is not just an economic issue but is also rooted in cultural, legal, and institutional practices. It critically examines discriminatory inheritance customs, restrictive land tenure systems, and male-dominated decision-making, underscoring the importance of collective action, solidarity, and advocacy for equitable land rights (Jacobs, 2004; Kachika, 2009).

Empowerment Theory

Rappaport (1981) introduced an empowerment theory that serves as a framework for understanding how marginalized groups gain control over their lives through engagement, resource access, and increased awareness. It defines empowerment as both a process where individuals build capacity and agency, and an outcome, reflected in improvements in economic and social status. For women in cooperatives, empowerment manifests through collective agency, allowing them to tackle challenges like restrictive tenure laws and financial exclusion. Cooperatives illustrate Rappaport's idea of 'power through collective action,' creating pathways for women to secure land rights, enhance food security, and promote community development. This research uses Empowerment Theory to frame women's land struggles within a broader context of resilience and structural change.

Complementary Theories of Crowdfunding

This study integrates feminist and empowerment frameworks with theories explaining motivations for crowdfunding participation, a key financing method for land acquisition. Social identification theory posits that individuals are more likely to support causes that resonate with them (Bamberger & Webb, 2015). The theory of planned behavior highlights how positive attitudes, social norms, and perceived control influence contributions. Social exchange theory points to non-monetary benefits like social recognition and emotional satisfaction, while cognitive evaluation theory stresses the importance of perceived value in motivating contributions (Smith & McKeen, 2012). Together, these theories clarify how crowdfunding can empower women in cooperatives to secure resources for land acquisition and community development.

Synthesis

Feminist Theory and Empowerment Theory form the core framework of this study, situating women's land rights within broader themes of social justice, agency, and gender equity. Additionally, crowdfunding participation theories enrich this framework by offering insights

into innovative financial strategies that can overcome structural barriers and enhance empowerment outcomes.

Conceptual Framework

This study identifies several barriers to women's land ownership, including discriminatory legal frameworks, inadequate land laws, insufficient financial capital, and gender norms. It also highlights the need for policies to ensure equal access to land for both males and females. The study concludes that crowdfunding can be a powerful tool for women in cooperatives to acquire land, thereby promoting economic empowerment and gender equality.

Conceptual Framework (Source: Authors)

Methods

The study focuses on the question: "What key factors, challenges, and strategies affect women's access to land through cooperatives in Eswatini?" While primarily quantitative, future studies could enhance understanding by incorporating mixed methods to capture personal narratives behind the data. This study used a quantitative methodology, collecting data through a structured questionnaire with closed-ended questions about land acquisition among women in cooperatives. The questionnaire was distributed to seven cooperatives: Lubane, Bunye Betfu Buhle Betfu, SNAT, Uneswa-Luyengo, Impumelelo, Sibonelo, and Eswatini Rural Women Assembly, targeting approximately 9,150 members (Kamar, 2019). To reduce sampling bias, simple random sampling was applied, with the sample size calculated using a specific formula.

$$n = Z^2(p(1-p)/ME^2), \tag{equation 1)}$$

where n is the sample size, Z² is the z-score, p is the proportion of individuals who are members of a cooperative (usually equal to 0.5), and ME is the margin of error.

From equation 1, it was determined that the optimal sample size was determined to be 92 respondents, selected randomly from the cooperative membership list based on their availability for telephone interviews. The research was conducted with a 95% confidence level and a 10% margin of error, with a proportion set at 60% (Creswell, 2017).

Ethical considerations were crucial for maintaining research integrity, involving permissions from cooperatives, a cover letter outlining the study's purpose, confidentiality measures (no names on questionnaires), and anonymization of data. Potential conflicts of interest were managed by allowing participants to disclose them freely. The questionnaire was translated from English to Siswati to address language barriers.

To ensure validity and reliability, a pilot study was conducted, and the Cronbach alpha (α) coefficient was applied (Finfgeld-Connett & Johnson, 2018; Middleton, 2019), with a score above 0.7 indicating the effective measurement of the intended variable.

Data Analysis and results

The study applied descriptive analysis and chi-square tests of association to determine the significance of different variables on land acquisition among women. Charts and graphs were used to present the data visually, where applicable. Data was captured and analysed using SPSS 20.

The study received 93 complete questionnaires, indicating a 100% response rate since the anticipated sample size of 92 respondents. Demographic information of participants was also discussed, including age, education level, and monthly income. Presentation of results includes demographic and socio-economic analysis, drivers, barriers, and strategies related to land acquisition among women in cooperatives. Discussion of drivers and barriers incorporates chi-squared tests of association to establish significant drivers and obstacles related to land acquisition among women in cooperatives.

Demographics and Socio-economic Analysis

Many respondents were aged 31 to 40 years, followed by those aged 41–45 and over 50 years. Nearly half (42%) of the respondents earned more than E6000 per month, categorizing them as high-income earners. Alongside the second-largest group earning between E4001 and E6000 (moderate-income), these two categories together accounted for 72% of the sample, indicating that most participants have moderate to high earnings. A smaller group earning between E2001 and E4000 falls into the middle-income bracket, with steady yet limited financial capacity. The smallest group, likely to earn below E2000, reflects low-income respondents who may face economic hardship and need additional support.

Figure 2. Demographic and socio-economic status of respondents

Drivers of Land Acquisition Among the Women in Cooperatives

This section explores the factors driving land acquisition among women in cooperatives in Eswatini. Figure 3 shows key drivers, including enhancing income, achieving economic empowerment, increasing asset accumulation, securing access to credit, ensuring household food security, affirming self-worth, maintaining independence, and pursuing entrepreneurial activities that motivate land acquisition among women in cooperatives. One key result is that the majority, composed of “strongly agree” and “agree”, of respondents identified all the drivers in Figure 2 as motivating them to acquire land.

Figure 3. Drivers of Land Acquisition Among Women

Economic Empowerment and Income Generation

Land ownership plays a crucial role in enhancing women's economic status, enabling them to actively engage in entrepreneurial ventures and agricultural production. The results indicate that a majority (83%) of participants identified economic empowerment and income generation as major motivating factors for acquiring land. This aligns with Kachika (2009), who states that complete control over land is necessary for the decrease of poverty and the fulfillment of the Millennium Development Goals. The empowerment not only allows women to generate income but also fosters a sense of agency and control over their financial futures. By owning land, women can cultivate crops, raise livestock, and explore various business opportunities,

thereby contributing to their households' economic well-being and the broader community (FAO, 2013).

Asset Accumulation

For a majority (88%) of the women surveyed, land is perceived as a vital asset that significantly contributes to their financial stability. Ownership of land provides women with a tangible resource that can be leveraged for economic advancement. Specifically, land can be used as collateral for loans, which facilitates access to credit and enables women to make additional investments in agriculture or small-scale businesses. As noted by Doss et al. (2011), women's authority over land directly influences their capacity to accumulate assets, thereby enhancing their bargaining power within households and communities. The security afforded by landownership enables women to engage in long-term planning, make independent financial choices, and mitigate their vulnerability to economic shocks. Consequently, land serves not merely as a productive asset but as a cornerstone for empowerment, resilience, and sustainable development for women.

Asset to credit

Access to credit is a vital element that affects women's capacity to obtain land. In this research, 67% of the women interviewed concurred that land ownership improves their chances of obtaining loans, indicating that land serves not only as a productive asset but also as significant collateral within formal financial frameworks. Nevertheless, women frequently encounter systemic obstacles when pursuing loans or other financial services, primarily due to gender biases, insufficient collateral, and inequitable inheritance rights. The World Bank (2012) emphasizes that women experience discrimination in land markets and credit systems, which limits their involvement in both redistributive reforms and land acquisition through purchase.

Food Security

Land ownership is directly linked to food security, especially for rural women in Eswatini. Secure access to land enables women to engage in agriculture, ensuring a reliable food supply for their families. In this study, 8 out of 10 of the women interviewed identified land as essential for food security, underscoring its role in sustainable livelihoods. This aligns with the FAO (2012), which states that women's land ownership enhances food security by enabling crop production and livestock rearing. Secure land tenure encourages women to adopt sustainable farming practices, improving productivity and resilience to food shortages. In Eswatini, where agriculture is vital and food insecurity is prevalent, women's access to land is crucial. It reduces dependence on external food sources, improves nutrition, and strengthens women's economic status in their families and communities (FAO, 2012; Slaymaker & Rowlands, 2012).

Self-Worth and Independence

Land ownership significantly enhances women's self-esteem and independence, particularly in settings where they face systemic barriers to economic participation. In this study, two-thirds of the women indicated that owning land is a major motivator, symbolizing autonomy and the ability to make impactful choices for themselves and their families. The (RDI, 2009) notes that land ownership fosters self-worth and provides security, enabling women to plan and engage more actively in their communities. Rao (2005) argues that property rights can reduce gender inequalities and lessen women's economic dependence on men, despite ongoing institutional discrimination. Jacobs (2004) highlights that in traditional societies like Eswatini, land often

symbolizes male dominance, making women's access to it fraught with social and legal challenges (Mutangadura, 2004). Duflo (2012) adds that cultural norms often keep men in key decision-making roles, even when women have legal property rights. Thus, land ownership can significantly enhance a woman's bargaining power, improving her economic outcomes, self-worth, and social standing.

Entrepreneurship

Land acquisition is crucial for entrepreneurship, with nearly half of women acknowledging its importance for starting businesses in agro-processing, livestock farming, and agriculture. Owning land provides women with resources to cultivate crops, raise animals, and create value-added products, leading to sustainable income. FAO (2011) notes that land ownership can serve as collateral for loans, enabling women to expand their businesses and explore new opportunities. This entrepreneurial participation not only promotes individual financial independence but also contributes to community development and economic growth. Mutangadura (2004) highlights that improving women's land tenure in Southern Africa, including Eswatini, can lead to job creation and poverty alleviation. Women's entrepreneurship empowers them and positively impacts community development as they reinvest in their families and inspire other women (Doss et al. 2007).

A further step using the chi-square analysis was made to test the relationship between crowdfunding as a solution to financing and the drivers of land acquisition among the women in stokvels/cooperatives. The correlation results measuring the relationship between crowdfunding as a solution to financing and the drivers of land acquisition among the women in stokvels show that none of the constructs of the drivers were statistically significant at $p < 0.05$ (Table 1). However, the need to acquire land to embark on entrepreneurial initiatives was statistically significant, $p < 0.1$. In this latter case, it implies that there is a strong positive relationship between crowdfunding as a solution to financing and the need to acquire land to embark on entrepreneurial initiatives, as depicted in Table 1. Simply, those who considered crowdfunding were also interested in acquiring land to embark on entrepreneurial initiatives.

Table 1. Chi-square test of association between crowdfunding as a solution to financing and the drivers of land acquisition among the women in stokvels/cooperatives

Drivers	Chi-Square Statistics	
	Coefficient	P-Value
I need to acquire land to improve my income level and for overall economic empowerment.	7.531	0.582
I need to acquire land to improve my asset accumulation.	11.999	0.213
I need to acquire land to facilitate access to credit	9.796	0.367
I need to acquire land to ensure food security in my household.	10.547	0.568
I need to acquire land to validate my self-worth.	15.671	0.207
I need to acquire land to maintain my independence and dignity.	15.405	0.22
I need to acquire land to embark on entrepreneurial initiatives	19.51	0.077

Barriers to Land Acquisition for Women in Cooperatives

Women involved in cooperatives face a multitude of challenges when it comes to acquiring land. These obstacles not only hinder their aspirations but also limit the overall potential of cooperatives to thrive and contribute to community development. Figure 4 shows the key obstacles to land ownership by women in cooperatives.

Figure 4. Obstacles to Land Acquisition for Women in Cooperatives

Financial Limitations

A significant barrier to land acquisition for women is financial constraints. A staggering three-quarters (77%) of participants in the survey cited low earnings as the foremost challenge, highlighting the broader difficulties encountered by women who are mainly involved in informal employment and subsistence agriculture. These fields generally provide limited and unstable income, hindering women's ability, particularly those in cooperatives, to save enough for land purchases. This financial instability is further intensified by limited access to credit, as numerous women do not possess the formal employment, credit history, or collateral that traditional banking institutions require.

Studies conducted by FAO (2011) and the World Bank (2012) validate that women in rural and informal sectors frequently experience systemic financial exclusion due to deep-rooted gender disparities in credit markets and institutional bias. In Eswatini, the scenario is further complicated by a dual legal system that may compromise women's financial autonomy and property rights under customary law (UN Women, 2020). In the absence of specific reforms aimed at fostering gender-sensitive financial inclusion, women continue to be structurally disadvantaged in land markets, which restricts their capacity to accumulate wealth and break free from cycles of poverty (Deere et al. 2011).

Cultural Norms and Gender Disparities

Cultural norms and deeply entrenched patriarchal traditions in Eswatini pose significant challenges to women's rights to land ownership. Over half (56%) of the respondents acknowledged that societal attitudes and resistance to women's property rights create an environment where women are discouraged from pursuing land ownership. This confirms the (Mutangadura, 2004) argument that women's land rights continue to face significant discrimination. These cultural barriers not only affect women's confidence but also perpetuate

the notion that land ownership is primarily a male domain, further marginalizing women in the agricultural and economic landscape.

Legal and Institutional Barriers

The complexity of land tenure systems and restrictive policies disproportionately affect women. More than half (54%) of respondents highlighted land tenure regulations as a significant challenge. Relating to other studies, this supports that inadequate implementation and enforcement of existing land laws hinder women's ability to acquire and secure land (Mubuu, 2013). The lack of legal acknowledgment often results in women being unable to claim land that they may have worked on or contributed to, thereby perpetuating cycles of poverty and inequality.

Insufficient Collateral and Awareness of Funding Options

The inability to provide sufficient collateral is another major hurdle for women seeking loans for land acquisition. Many women lack valuable assets that could be used as security for loans, which limits their borrowing capacity. Additionally, there is a notable gap in awareness regarding alternative funding options, such as crowdfunding or community-based financing initiatives. This lack of knowledge further restricts women's opportunities to explore diverse financial avenues that could facilitate land acquisition.

Level of Education

Education plays a crucial role in empowering women to engage in land acquisition activities. According to a study focused on the Khwisero Constituency in Kenya's Kakamega County, a lack of knowledge was the biggest obstacle to women owning land there (Gail, 2016). In contrast to this study, many respondents did not perceive education as a barrier; only a notable 24% highlighted that lower literacy rates and limited legal knowledge pose significant challenges (Rünger, 2006). Women with lower levels of education may struggle to navigate the complexities of land acquisition processes, including understanding legal documents, negotiating contracts, and advocating for their rights. This lack of knowledge can lead to missed opportunities and exploitation, as women may be less equipped to challenge unfair practices or to fully comprehend the implications of land ownership. Furthermore, the absence of educational resources tailored to women's needs can exacerbate these challenges, leaving them at a disadvantage in a predominantly male-dominated field. A study that was done in Ghana confirms this, stating that Ghanaian women frequently have lower incomes and lower literacy rates than men (Rünger, 2006).

A further step using the chi-square analysis was made to test the relationship between crowdfunding as a solution to financing and the obstacles of land acquisition among the women in stokvels/cooperatives. Table 2 shows correlation results measuring the relationship between crowdfunding as a solution to financing and the barriers to land acquisition. Table 4 shows that three of the seven constructs on the barriers were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). These constructs are limited income level hinders access to land barrier (chi-square coefficient = 25.151, $p = 0.014$); lack of assets or collateral hinders my access to land (chi-square coefficient = 22.937, $p = 0.028$); and my level of education hinders my access to land (chi-square coefficient = 22.104, $p = 0.036$).

Firstly, these results reveal that those who considered crowdfunding as a solution to financing faced limited income level as a barrier to accessing land as a barrier. Secondly, those who considered crowdfunding as a solution to financing also had a barrier of a lack of assets or

collateral that hinders their access to land. Lastly, those who considered crowdfunding as a solution to financing also had a barrier to their level of education, as well as a barrier to their access to land, as shown by Table 2. The existing land tenure laws as a hindrance to access to land were marginally statistically significant at $p < 0.1$.

Table 2. Chi-square test of association between crowdfunding and barriers to land acquisition

Barriers	Chi-Square Statistics	
	Coefficient	P-Value
Limited income hinders my access to land.	25.151	0.014
Cultural norms hinder my access to land	14.195	0.288
The existing land tenure laws hinder my access to land	16.899	0.091
Lack of assets or collateral hinders my access to land.	22.937	0.028
Limited knowledge of funding options for land acquisition hinders my access to land	13.47	0.336
Gender disparities around land ownership hinder my access to land	13.307	0.347
My level of education hinders my access to land	22.104	0.036

Strategies for Land Acquisition by Women in Cooperatives

The study also explored strategies for land acquisition by women in cooperatives, focusing on key areas: revising land tenure laws to include women's rights, utilizing crowdfunding for land purchases, offering tax incentives to encourage women's participation in real estate, changing cultural norms to combat discrimination, improving access to credit for women, addressing gender disparities in the real estate sector, and promoting educational programs on land ownership for women.

Figure 5. Strategies for land acquisition among women in cooperatives in Eswatini

The most widely supported (a total of 86% of respondents either strongly agreed or agreed) approach involves the establishment of intermediate courses on land acquisition and ownership, specifically designed for women by training institutions. This initiative addresses the necessity for skill development and education aimed at empowering women within the real estate sector. In a similar vein, Ikdaahl et al. (2005) posited that the effectiveness of women's land rights is obstructed by gender-biased norms and practices that predominantly benefit men. Following this, the call to address gender disparities emphasizes the importance of achieving gender equity in land ownership. Additionally, the use of crowdfunding as a financing mechanism and the enhancement of credit access for women ranked third in support, with approximately 80% of respondents endorsing these measures. These recommendations underscore the financial obstacles faced by women and the urgent need for innovative funding solutions, as highlighted by the UN (2010).

Furthermore, three-quarters of the respondents concurred that revising land tenure laws to be more inclusive of women's land rights represents an effective solution, underscoring the critical role of policy reforms in dismantling systemic barriers. However, only 66% of women expressed support for the implementation of tax incentives for those investing in real estate, such as property tax deductions or capital gains exemptions for women-owned properties, aimed at providing financial relief and encouraging land acquisition. Lastly, 63% of respondents acknowledged that cultural transformation is vital for eradicating discrimination against women in land ownership.

This study has several limitations. First, it relies on a small sample of cooperative members from Eswatini, which may limit the findings' applicability elsewhere. Second, the use of self-reported survey data introduces potential response bias, as participants may exaggerate or minimize their experiences. Third, the exclusive focus on quantitative methods, while statistically rigorous, limits the understanding of personal narratives and social dynamics that qualitative approaches could better explore. Addressing these limitations in future research would strengthen the evidence on women's access to land in sub-Saharan Africa.

Conclusion, recommendations, and further research

The acquisition of land is fundamental to the economic empowerment of women in Eswatini. Land ownership not only provides women with a tangible asset but also serves as a critical foundation for financial independence, enabling them to invest in their families, communities, and businesses. However, to realize this potential, it is essential to address the multifaceted obstacles that hinder women's access to land. These challenges include limited income, which restricts women's ability to purchase or lease land; entrenched cultural practices that may prioritize male ownership; and insufficient funding opportunities that leave women without the necessary financial resources to secure land rights.

To facilitate women's land ownership and promote their financial autonomy, a multifaceted approach is required. Innovative strategies such as crowdfunding can empower women by pooling resources from a broader community, thereby enabling them to acquire land collectively. Additionally, policy changes that promote gender equality in land ownership are vital. This includes revising existing laws and regulations to ensure that women have equal rights to land and access to legal recourse in cases of disputes. Furthermore, educational programs aimed at raising awareness about women's rights to land and providing training in land management and agricultural practices can equip women with the knowledge and skills needed to navigate the complexities of land ownership.

Strengthened collaboration among cooperatives, governmental bodies, and financial institutions is crucial for achieving sustainable development and gender equality in land ownership. By fostering partnerships that leverage the strengths of each stakeholder, it is possible to create a more equitable real estate environment. Cooperatives can provide a support network for women, while government initiatives can create a regulatory framework that promotes gender-inclusive policies. Financial institutions can play a pivotal role by developing tailored financial products that cater to the unique needs of women seeking to acquire land.

In summary, empowering women through land ownership is not only a matter of social justice but also a catalyst for economic growth and community development in Eswatini. By addressing the barriers to land access and implementing comprehensive strategies that promote women's rights, we can pave the way for a more equitable society where women can thrive as landowners, entrepreneurs, and leaders. The journey towards gender equality in land ownership is a collective effort that requires commitment, collaboration, and sustained action from all sectors of society.

Recommendations

To tackle gender inequalities in real estate, most respondents support targeted interventions for land acquisition. Additionally, specialized courses on land ownership for women could be beneficial. Key strategies include:

Encourage Young Women's Participation in Cooperatives by actively recruiting young women through outreach in schools, workshops on cooperative benefits, and mentorship programs linking them with experienced members. Enhance Access to Legal Knowledge by Providing women with legal education on land rights through workshops, brochures, and online resources to empower them in navigating legal processes. Facilitate Women's Participation in Land Acquisition Groups by establishing women-only land acquisition groups to create safe spaces for collaboration and advocacy on land rights. Offering Financial Support and Improving Credit Access to encourage financial institutions to develop tailored products like microloans and grants to support women in land acquisition and cooperative projects. Lastly, develop Mentorship and Networking Opportunities to create mentorship initiatives to connect women with experienced professionals in the field.

Further Studies

Future investigations should assess the effectiveness of policies protecting women's land rights to understand their impact and outcomes, identifying strengths and weaknesses for improvement. Longitudinal studies are vital for tracking changes in women's land ownership and empowerment over time, providing insights into trends and long-term policy effects. Additionally, further research is needed to analyze how current policies address gender inequalities in land acquisition, considering economic, social, and cultural factors. Identifying barriers women face can highlight legislative gaps and inform targeted interventions. In summary, a comprehensive approach involving policy evaluations, longitudinal studies, and analyses of gender inequalities is essential for advancing women's land rights and promoting gender equity.

Disclosure Statement

No potential conflict of interest.

Notes on Contributors

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